

Impact of Linguistic Diversity in Post Independent India

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Abstract: This paper investigates a detailed explication of the “Impact of Linguistic diversity in post-independent India” and its development process from independence to the present scenario. In post-independent India, the linguistic context has played a crucial role in shaping India’s social, political, and cultural fabric. Since India gained independence in 1947, linguistic diversity has influenced various aspects of Indian society. As a country with a diverse range of languages, India faces a unique set of challenges as well as opportunities. The research examines the linguistic policies implemented by the Indian government to promote linguistic harmony among diverse linguistic social groups. It also examines how language shapes regional identities, political affiliations, and cultural dimensions. A study examines the challenges posed by linguistic diversity in governance, education, and social integration, looking at both the positive and negative contributions and also potential tensions related to linguistic diversity. This research examines historical developments, policy changes, and social dynamics to gain a deeper understanding of how linguistic diversity shapes the contemporary Indian experience. A more inclusive and harmonious society in post-independent India can only be achieved by recognizing and managing linguistic diversity.

Keywords: Commission, Constitution, Democracy, Linguistic Diversity, Post independence Society, State Reorganization

Background of Study: Post-independence India inherited vast linguistic diversity, which shaped its geopolitical landscape. This study investigates how language affects national integration, regional identity, and policymaking. It explores the challenges and opportunities presented by multilingualism, with a particular emphasis on education, government, and cultural preservation within a complex, democratic environment.

Objectives: The present paper examines the concept of the ‘Impact of Linguistic Diversity in Post-Independent India and its historical context, key developments, and multifaceted outcomes, prospects, and challenges. The primary objective of this paper is to analyze how India's post-independence identity has been shaped by language and its positive and negative consequences on people. The paper analyzes the merits, challenges, and potential of the ‘Impact of Linguistic Diversity in Post-Independent India’ in India’s political landscape.

Methodology: In this paper, secondary data is generally taken as a source from various books, research papers, articles, newspapers, and government reports. The aim is to identify

and analyze the existing literature on the diversity of linguistic identity issues since independence.

1. Introduction

India began its journey as an independent nation in 1947 and has a rich variety of linguistic, cultural, and ethnic varieties. India's post-independence linguistic environment has been crucial in determining the nation's socio-political dynamics, cultural identity, and economic paths. With 121 primary languages approximately spoken throughout the country and 22 legally recognized languages according to the constitution, India has unprecedented linguistic diversity. Thus, an inventory of classified mother tongues returned by 10,000 or more speakers grouped under appropriate languages at the all-India level, wherever possible, has been prepared for the final presentation of the 2011 mother tongue data. The total number of languages arrived at is 121 [1]. This language variety has presented special opportunities as well as challenges in the areas of social integration, governance, and education, in addition to being a source of strength and resilience. The makers of India's constitution recognized the value of linguistic diversity once the country became independent and included specific articles protecting the rights and interests of linguistic minorities. However linguistic diversity has far-reaching impacts in post-independent India that go well beyond the words of the constitution. It has had a significant impact on educational fields, political movements, and the development of regional identities. To better understand the complicated implications of the variety of languages in post-independent India, this study will look at how it affects cohesiveness in society; political representation, economic growth, and the country's overall development. The objective of the present paper investigate the concept of the 'Impact of Linguistic Diversity in Post-Independent India. and its historical context, prospects, and challenges. The primary objective of this paper is to analyze how India's post-independence identity has been shaped by linguistic diversity. While India's linguistic diversity is generally recognized, little study has been conducted on the intersection of language and internal migration in post-independence India. While much has been written about the differences between Hindi and regional languages, tribal, and endangered languages have received less attention since independence. These gaps highlight the need for a more inclusive understanding of linguistic impact in contemporary India.

2. Linguistic diversity means

Language diversity can be observed at a number of levels, ranging from the global diversity of languages spoken worldwide to the local or regional variations within a specific area of the world. Besides enhancing the uniqueness of different communities and contributing to the formation of identities, it is a basic part of human culture as well [2]. It's essential to keep in mind that India has a diverse range of languages, depending on the variety of language groups to which these languages belong. India is home to several main language families, including Dravidian, Austro-Asiatic, Indo-Aryan, and Tibeto-Burman. Every language family has a unique set of languages that add to the nation's overall linguistic fabric. The Constitution of India recognizes the importance of preserving and maintaining linguistic diversity, and it includes provisions that enhance the rights of minorities of various languages within the country. To accommodate the board range of languages and cultures, Indian states are frequently organized according to linguistic basis. Although India's linguistic

diversity adds to its cultural diversity, it also creates administrative and interactive challenges.

3. Historical background

India is noted for having a large number of languages spoken throughout the country as a whole. India has a variety of linguistic surroundings that have been formed by social, cultural, and historical influences.

- (i) **Ancient Period:** The history of India's linguistic diversity dates back thousands of years. Although a script that has not yet been deciphered (because usually it was written in pictographic style) is thought to have been from the Indus Valley Civilization (c. 3300–1300 BCE), linguistic diversity was likely to be present even at that time. India's linguistic diversity is a combination of languages, each of which adds to the country's rich cultural heritage. Classical Indian literature is in Sanskrit, but it was not the official language of the whole length and breadth of India as it exists today. Sanskrit was spoken by elites, or the working language of the official class, but was not used by common people at that time.
- (ii) **Medieval Period:** In the Moghul period, Persian became the language of the courts and offices, but during this period, Urdu was developed as the language of the masses, and Hindi was also written and spoken. Regional languages known as Prakrit emerged throughout the medieval era, many of which developed into contemporary Indian languages. For instance, some areas of the Delhi region's Khari Boli dialect gave rise to Hindi.
- (iii) **Colonial Period:** The linguistic diversity of India was significantly impacted by British colonialism (1757–1947). The official language of administration and education at that time was English. The foundation for the acknowledgement of linguistic diversity was established by the British census (1921), which listed and classified the numerous languages spoken, all over India. With a large number of languages spoken there, India is still a linguistically diverse country [3].

4. Linguistic diversity and constitution

India is a vast country where several languages are used by people with their scripts. This linguistic diversity exists because of our rich culture and the diverse community that inhabited this land. Other factors of linguistic diversity are trade, migration, conquest, and colonialism. With hundreds of languages spoken throughout its extensive territory, the Indian Constitution mentions 22 official languages. India has been known for its linguistic diversity since achieving independence in 1947. This diversity has greatly influenced the social, political, and economic status of our country.

Freedom struggle and resultant independence brought the issue of an Official Language, freedom fighters wanted the Indian language as the official language of independent India. It was a difficult task to announce any one language as an official language because no such language was used and accepted throughout the territory of India. Linguistic affinity has served as a basis for organizing interest groups; the "language question" itself has become an increasingly sensitive political issue. Efforts to reach a consensus on a single national language that transcends the myriad linguistic regions and is acceptable to diverse language communities have been largely unsuccessful [4].

In the draft constitution, article 99 stated that the language of parliament shall be Hindi or English, it did not talk about the official language because the question of language creates division in the constituent assembly. The language framework of the nation was significantly impacted by the language disputes held within the Constituent Assembly of India, which assembled from December 1946 to November 1949 to establish the Indian Constitution. The official language of the Union, the language used by the government and courts, and the protection and development of regional languages were all topics of debate during the Assembly's language sessions. These conversations emphasized India's multilingualism and the difficulties in creating a cohesive national identity that takes this variety into account. Sh. R.V., Dhuleker's statement in the constituent assembly on December 10, 1946, as people who do not speak Hindustani do not have the right to stay in India. People who are in this house to draft a constitution for India but do not speak Hindustani are unfit to be members of this assembly [5].

During the Constituent Assembly Debates on September 17, 1949, Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar discussed language issues about the proposed Constitution. Given India's great diversity, he underlined the significance of not forcing any one language on the entire country. Ambedkar advocated for the continued use of English alongside Hindi for official Union purposes for a transitional period of 15 years from the start of the Constitution, even though Hindi was ultimately chosen as the official language. This demonstrates his inclusive approach to linguistic diversity and was done to guarantee that areas that do not speak Hindi were not feeling at a disadvantage [6].

The Objectives Resolution, which set forth the goals and principles of the upcoming constitution, was introduced by Nehru. The issue of language was not specifically addressed; this implicitly created the foundation for later linguistic regulations by setting an example for a nation that valued diversity and togetherness. Nehru was in favour of Hindi being the official language of India, but he also thought that English should remain an associate official language for as long as possible, until Hindi gained enough strength to replace English in all governmental roles. This was a practical strategy to maintain effectiveness in administration and continuity while promoting Hindi. Nehru placed considerable value on the preservation and promotion of regional languages because he recognized the cultural and emotional importance of language. To foster linguistic diversity, he believed it was critical to let states operate their affairs in the languages native to their regions.

After a detailed discussion and emotional debate on the issue of official language in the constituent assembly, Hindi in Devanagari script was adopted as the official language, and English as an associate official language only for 15 years of the union. The language policy of India is embodied in Part XVII of the Indian Constitution. This part is divided into four chapters dealing with the language of the Union, regional languages, the language of the Supreme Court and High Court, and special directives, respectively. Part XVII, along with 8th schedule articles 344 and 351 (which specify the languages of India for purposes mentioned in these two articles), and the articles concerning Fundamental Rights regarding language, education, culture, etc. [7].

5. Indian States and Multilingualism

The language policy gives full freedom to the states, according to articles 346 and 347, to choose any language or languages spoken in regions as their regional languages and to have one or more of them as official languages by different states. All the states have declared or adopted their Official Language.

The following are some of the policies that the Indian government uses to encourage multilingualism:

- (i) **Three Language Formula:** The Three-Language Formula promotes national integration and cross-cultural understanding by encouraging students to study three languages in school: the regional language, Hindi (in places where Hindi is not spoken), and English. This approach is designed to promote unity in diversity, making it require that students in Hindi-speaking states learn a modern Indian language from other parts of India, while students from non-Hindi - speaking states learn Hindi along with their regional language and English. The choice of language learned by students will depend on the individual state and the choice of the students and their families. This flexibility is aimed at accommodating diverse linguistic backgrounds in the country and ensuring that the three - languages formula is inclusive [8]. There were some shortcomings of the three-language formula on implementation grounds. States such as Tamil Nadu were highly opposed to learning Hindi, perceiving it as an imposition. Hindi-speaking states were frequently less enthusiastic about acquiring South Indian languages. Different governments interpreted the formula differently: some emphasized English, while others prioritized Hindi or regional languages, resulting in uncertainty and inconsistency. Identity is closely associated with language. Implementing a "national" formula resulted in political protests and encouraged regional pride groups.
- (ii) **Official Languages Act, 1963:** The Official Languages Act permits the Union government to utilize Hindi and English for official purposes. The Language Policy of India relating to the use of languages in administration, education, judiciary, legislature, mass communication, etc., is pluralistic in its scope. In intergovernmental communication, Hindi is to be used where the state has adopted Hindi as official language and where Hindi has not be so adopted, communication is required to be in English [9]. States and their main major languages list are given below:

S. No.	States	Major language
1	Haryana, Bihar, Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Uttarakhand	Hindi
2	Kerala, Punjab, Gujarat	Malayalam, Punjabi, Gujarati
3	West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh, Telangana	Bangla, Telugu, Telugu
4	Odisha, Mizoram, Maharashtra	Odia, Lushai, Marathi
5	Goa, Meghalaya, Tripura, Manipur	Konkani, Khasi, Bengali, Manipuri
6	Sikkim, Assam, Arunachal Pradesh	Nepali, Assamese, Nissi
7	Nagaland, Tamilnadu, Karnataka,	Ao, Tamil, Kannada
8	Himachal Pradesh, Chhattisgarh	Bharmauri, Chhattisgarhi

Source: *Linguistic Survey of India, Census Report 2011* [10]

India's linguistic policy, which reflects the nation's complex social fabric and dedication to unity in diversity, is intended to protect linguistic diversity while fostering communication across linguistic boundaries. But the concept of development based on pluralistic uses of language failed to keep its potential. The language created a great problem in the post-independent era and continues to be one of the heavyweights on the country's political system even today. People have been promised by mainstream political leaders during the days of freedom struggle that the free India will be open for the development of all its languages but with time this become only the agenda of winning elections by the political parties.

India got her independence in 1947 and even today language problem persists. It is still a heavy weight on the Indian political system and the issue is so sensitive that it can be exploited at any time by some politicians to serve their ends and purposes. Many politicians do not hesitate to make the language an issue as and when the need arises [11].

6. Formation of State on linguistic basis

The British had left behind a map that was more a legacy of imperial convenience than a reflection of the socio-cultural realities of the Indian subcontinent. Thereafter gaining independence from British domination in 1947, India faced numerous obstacles in its nation-building process. One of the most significant was the restructurization of its states. The post-independence period saw a strong drive towards restructuring the nation's administrative boundaries on a linguistic basis. This movement was grounded in the belief that linguistic states would ensure administrative convenience, promote cultural unity, and strengthen national unification. The reorganization of states on a linguistic basis in India stands as an outstanding example of how language can serve as a cornerstone in nation-building efforts.

Initially, the Indian National Congress was wary, fearing that linguistic states could lead to regionalism and weaken the fabric of the newly independent states. However, it was hard to ignore the calls for states to be divided along linguistic lines due to the linguistic variety of India and the profound cultural and historical value of languages. With post independence, the belief that speakers of a common language ought to set up their own state led to an increase in the demand for linguistic states. As numerous language communities sought to reorganize states along linguistic lines, the concept gained strength in the 1950s and 1960s.

Reorganisation Act: An important turning point was the linguistic restructuring of states in 1956, which established linguistic lines as well as linguistic boundaries to creating new states. This background information lays the groundwork for comprehending the effects of linguistic diversity today. S.K. Dhar commission and JVP committee advocated for reorganization of states, based on geographical contiguity, administrative convenience, financial self reliance and potential for development, but not on the linguistic basis because Hindi – Urdu language controversy(Hindi for Hindu community and Urdu used by Muslim community) became also one of the reasons behind India – Pakistan partition [12].

(i) Formation of Andhra Pradesh (1953) and Fazl Ali Commission

Background: Potti Sriramalu following a long hunger strike against these reports demanded Andhra state on a linguistic basis. The Telugu Language Movement was a prominent linguistic movement that sought to establish a distinct state for those who spoke

Telugu. One of the earliest linguistic reorganizations of states in post-independence India occurred in 1953 with the creation of Andhra Pradesh, the result of this movement. At first, there was a call for the creation of the linguistic state of Andhra, distinct from the predominantly Tamil-speaking Madras Presidency. A widespread movement known as the "Jai Andhra" movement was one of the major events that set off this demand.

Fazl Ali Commission: Due to the long hunger strike, Potti Sriramalu's sudden death created the volatile situation and the States Reorganization Commission 1956 also known as the Fazl Ali Commission was set up which was led by Justice Fazal Ali. The commission, after careful consideration of the cultural, linguistic, and economic aspects, suggested the restructuring of states. The Act significantly altered the political landscape of India by resulting in the formation of 14 states and 6 union territories. This landmark legislation was a response to several national movements and agitations across the country, the most notable being the demand for the creation of Andhra Pradesh, for Telugu-speaking people, which became the first state to be formed on a linguistic basis in 1953, even before the Act was passed [13].

Consequences: The action was taken to promote language identity as well as address differences between regions. As a result of the linguistic reorganization in 1956, linguistic boundaries were recognized and states were created based on linguistic lines. This historical context sets the stage for understanding linguistic diversity in the present. The need for efficient government and cultural supremacy frequently led to the demand for linguistic states. The political and social climate in India was significantly impacted by the linguistic restructuring of the states. It enabled improved governance by increasing public accessibility to administration. Additionally, it was essential in maintaining and advancing the linguistic and cultural variety of India by elevating regional languages and cultures inside their states. Over time, administrative effectiveness and economic feasibility have been added to the linguistic premise, resulting in the formation of new states including, Maharashtra(1960), Punjab and Haryana (1966), Tamil Nadu (1969), Himachal Pradesh (1971), Karnataka(1973), Chhattisgarh, Uttarakhand, and Jharkhand (2000), Telangana (2014) etc.

(ii) Formation of Maharashtra(1960)

Background: Maharashtra's establishment as a state primarily for Marathi-speaking people was pivotal moment in the history of India's linguistic restructuring. The linguistic and cultural uniformity of the Indian people was not reflected in the internal political borders that were left over from the British era after India gained independence. A popular desire for the rearrangement of the states along linguistic lines resulted from this imbalance. One of the most important movements at this time was the call for a separate state for Marathi-speaking people.

Movement: The movement for a separate Maharashtra, known as the Samyukta Maharashtra Movement, was a major component of the advocacy for the linguistic reorganization of states. This movement called for the creation of a separate state for Marathi-speaking people. Bombay (now Mumbai) becomes the capital of a separate state for Marathi-speaking people. The movement was marked by mass protests, marches, and the active participation of various political parties, trade unions, and cultural organizations.

Reorganization Act: The States Reorganization Act, of 1956, was the official government of India's response to the linguistic restructuring of the states. The original plan, which called for a bilingual state of Bombay with Bombay City as its capital and areas speaking both Gujarati and Marathi, did not, however, satisfy the aspirations of the Samyukta Maharashtra Movement. After more unrest due to dissatisfaction with this idea, the movement's objectives were eventually met on May 1, 1960, when the state of Maharashtra was established. The capital of Maharashtra, Bombay, was included in the state.

Consequences: The establishment of a state along linguistic lines boosted the sense of togetherness and pride among Marathi-speaking people, resulting in a stronger regional identity. The linguistic formation fuelled the rise of regional political organizations such as the Shiv Sena, which fought for the rights of Marathi-speaking people and played an important role in Maharashtra politics. While cities like Mumbai and Pune thrived, regions like Vidarbha and Marathwada faced economic issues, prompting calls for more divisions based on regional differences.

(iii) Formation of Punjab and Haryana(1966)

Background: Before the partition of India in 1947, Punjab was a major province that included areas now in Pakistan. The partition led to a massive demographic and geographic shift, with West Punjab becoming part of Pakistan and East Punjab staying in India. Post-independence, the region saw the merger of several princely states into the PEPSU (Patiala and East Punjab States Union), which eventually merged with Punjab in 1956, consolidating the Punjabi-speaking regions [14].

Movement: The demand for a Punjabi Suba (state) movement was primarily spearheaded by the Akali Dal, a Sikh-dominated political party. The Akali Dal led this campaign, which had its roots in both religious and linguistic identity. The linguistic rearrangement of states elsewhere in India (such as the formation of Andhra Pradesh for Telugu speakers in 1956) provided a precedent and momentum for this movement. The movement saw opposition, particularly from those who identified Hindi as their mother tongue in the regions that would later become Haryana [15]. The concerns were not just linguistic but also religious and cultural, given the significant Hindu population in the areas supporting Hindi.

Reorganization Act: The union government, after much discussion and in response to growing demands (and following significant agitation and protests), approved the Punjab Reorganization Act, of 1966 [16]. This act led to the creation of Punjab and Haryana as separate states on November 1, 1966.

Consequences: The aim was to establish a state where the main population would be Sikh, setting it apart from the areas where Hindi is spoken [17]. They argued for a separate state for Punjabi - speaking people to protect and promote the Punjabi language and Sikh culture.

(iv) Formation of Tamilnadu (1969)

Background: Tamil Nadu was earlier a part of the Madras Presidency under British control. In the early 20th century, the demand for linguistic states gained momentum with leaders, officials and scholars emphasizing the need for administrative units to reflect the language and culture of the regions.

Movement: The formation of Tamil Nadu as a state on a linguistic basis is an important development in the history of Indian state reorganization. The process was part of a broader

movement that sought to redraw the internal boundaries of India to better represent the cultural and linguistic identities of its people [18]. This represented a change from the sometimes arbitrary administrative divisions that were carried over from the British colonial era, which were often arbitrary and did not consider ethnic, linguistic, or cultural harmony.

Reorganization Act: After much discussion and based on the recommendations of the States Reorganization Commission established in 1953, the States Reorganisation Act of 1956 ultimately led to the creation of Tamil Nadu. The former Madras State was renamed Tamil Nadu on January 14, 1969, to emphasize the Tamil language and cultural legacy [19]. This statute rebuilds states along linguistic lines.

Consequences: The reformation solidified Tamil language and cultural identities. Tamils, who had previously felt excluded in a multilingual Madras State, earned a stronger feeling of togetherness and pride. The term "Tamil Nadu" (meaning "land of Tamils") acknowledged the importance of Tamil language and culture [20]. It fostered a strong sense of identity, political empowerment of regional parties, and an enduring legacy of linguistic pride that continues to shape Tamil Nadu today.

(v) Formation of Himachal Pradesh (1971)

Background: The hilly areas of the old Punjab state, which were predominantly Hindi-speaking but had not been actively involved in the demand for a separate state, were combined into the Union territory of Himachal Pradesh, which later became a full-fledged state. The region that is now Himachal Pradesh has been inhabited since ancient times. It has seen the rule of several dynasties over the centuries, like the Mauryas, Guptas, and Mughals, among others. During British rule in India, the region was organized into various princely states, with Shimla becoming an important summer capital and administrative center.

Reorganization Act: The Punjab Reorganization Act of 1966 led to a significant geographical reorganization. Parts of the state of Punjab, which were Hindi-speaking, were combined to form Himachal Pradesh [21]. This significantly increased the geographical area and population of Himachal Pradesh.

Movement: The Punjab Reorganization Act had a linguistic element, as it aimed to recombine territories based on the dominant languages spoken by the population. As a result, the Hindi-speaking regions of the Punjab region were transferred to Himachal Pradesh. Not linguistic uniformity, though, was the main driving force behind the establishment and growth of Himachal Pradesh; rather, it was political unification and administrative efficiency. Himachal Pradesh became the 25th state to be admitted into the Indian Union on January 25, 1971 [22].

Consequences: While the state's formation had factors of linguistic considerations, particularly during the 1966 reorganization, Himachal Pradesh is characterized by a wide diversity of languages and dialects. Hindi is the official language and is extensively spoken, but the state is also home to various Pahari languages and dialects. Each region, valley, and district have its unique cultural and linguistic heritage, contributing to the state's diverse cultural landscape.

(vi) Formation of North Eastern States

Nagaland (1963), Meghalaya (1972), Mizoram (1987), and Arunachal Pradesh (1987)

Background: The eight states (Assam, Nagaland, Manipur, Mizoram, Tripura, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, and Sikkim) that make up the Northeast area of India are renowned for their incredible ethnic, linguistic, and cultural diversity. In order to facilitate good governance, better administration, and the preservation of cultural and linguistic harmony, the notion of reorganizing states based on language mostly arises from the desire to establish administrative and political entities where the majority of people speak the same language [23].

Movement: The Northeast is home to approximately 200 ethnic groups and an equal number of dialects, with each state having its own set of languages and dialects. Due to the region's ethnic variety and overlapping language and cultural identities that do not properly fit into the linguistic-state framework found elsewhere in India, the linguistic restructuring in this area has proven to be a problematic subject.

Reorganization: The most significant linguistic reorganization in the Northeast took place when the areas that were once a part of Assam were divided into Nagaland (1963), Meghalaya (1972), Mizoram (1987), and Arunachal Pradesh (1987). A combination of political, linguistic, and ethnic considerations led to this rearrangement. For example, Meghalaya was made for the Garo, Khasi, and Jaintia tribes; and Mizoram was made for the Mizo tribes; Arunachal Pradesh was made for the numerous tribal groups, each of which had its own language and dialect. Nagaland was made for the Naga tribes [24].

Consequences: The formation of linguistically different states reduced conflicts between major ethnic groupings. For example, the Khasi, Garo, and Jaintia tribes in Meghalaya gained a unique political space, free of Assamese dominance [25]. Despite new state formations, insurgencies remained, fuelled by disappointments, ethnic rivalries, and cross-border connections (e.g., with Myanmar and Bangladesh). Even today, the Northeast remains strongly militarized [26].

(vii) Formation of Karnataka (1973)

The creation of Karnataka, previously known as the State of Mysore, is a most important event in the history of South India. On November 1, 1973, the State of Mysore was officially renamed as Karnataka. The consolidation of Kannada-speaking regions to form the state is an important aspect of its history, which was achieved through the States Reorganization Act of 1956 [27].

(viii) Formation of Chhattisgarh (2000)

Background: The formation of Chhattisgarh was influenced by several issues beyond linguistic identity, including economic and administrative concerns. Rather than being exclusively determined by linguistic standards, the creation of Chhattisgarh as a unique state in India was impacted by a number of variables, such as cultural identity and linguistic difference.

Movement: The Chhattisgarhi people's cultural and linguistic identity—speaking a Hindi dialect called Chhattisgarhi—was crucial to the statehood campaign.

Reorganization Act: Finally, with the consent of President K. R. Narayanan, the Madhya Pradesh Reorganization Act of August 25, 2000, separated Chhattisgarh from Madhya Pradesh. The government of India set November 1, 2000, as the day Chhattisgarh state was formed [28].

Consequences: Given its abundant mineral resources and the need for more focused governance in the area, Chhattisgarh was formed with considerations of economy and administration. Unlike the formation of states like Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, or Tamil Nadu, which were primarily based on linguistic lines.

(ix) Formation of Uttarakhand (2000)

Background: The region of Uttarakhand is situated in the northern part of India, comprising an important region of the Himalayas. It is characterized by a distinct linguistic identity, with languages such as Garhwali, Jaunsari, and Kumaoni being widely spoken, among others. The Central Pahari group of languages distinguishes the linguistic and cultural character of the region from the neighbouring regions of Uttar Pradesh. The linguistic basis for the formation of Uttarakhand is connected with its cultural and historical importance, leading to a demand for a separate state that could provide good governance, economic development, and preservation of its cultural heritage.

Movement: The people of Uttarakhand felt that their unique cultural and linguistic heritage was being ignored by the administrative units of Uttar Pradesh. The demand for a separate state based on linguistic and cultural identity began to peak in the late 20th century. They argued that a separate state would allow them to preserve their linguistic heritage and preserve regional languages and cultures that had been marginalized [29]. The linguistic and cultural identity of the region, however, played a major role in mobilizing support for statehood and was a central theme in the statehood movement.

Reorganization: The formation of Uttarakhand as a separate state was finally created on November 9, 2000, when it was divided from Uttar Pradesh. The region suffered from socioeconomic negligence and environmental degradation under the rule of a remote government headquartered in Lucknow, which served as further motivation for the statehood movement beyond language differences.

(x) Formation of Jharkhand (2000)

Background: The concept of Jharkhand, which means 'forest territory,' has been closely linked with the tribal groups that inhabit the region, notably the Santhal, Munda, Ho, and Oraon communities.

Movement: The Indo-Aryan languages that predominate in the nearby regions are different from the Austro-Asiatic and Dravidian language families; these tribes speak distinct languages [30]. These tribes' similar socio-cultural traditions, marginalization experiences, and language coherence provided a strong basis for the desire for their own state. With language acting as a vital indicator of ethnic and cultural identity, the region's many tribal tribes were able to unite. The Jharkhand movement's main demands were the recognition of these languages and the assurance of their promotion and maintenance. Proponents said that having a distinct state would enable the implementation of better developmental and educational programs that are adapted to the regional language and cultural differences [31].

Reorganization: After decades of activism and political polarization, Jharkhand was officially formed on November 15, 2000, when it was carved out of the southern region of Bihar. This historic decision was influenced by the recognition of the distinct linguistic and cultural identity of the region's tribal communities.

Consequences: It was anticipated that the establishment of the state would bring about more considerate and inclusive government, particularly in the fields of economic growth, education, and the preservation of language and culture. The linguistic identity of Jharkhand played a major role in promoting the move towards a separate state.

(xi) Formation of Telangana (2014)

Background: Telangana became the 29th state of India on June 2, 2014, marking the culmination of a long-standing movement driven by linguistic, socio-economic, and cultural reasons. Numerous causes encouraged the call for Telangana to become an independent state. The main factor was linguistic identity, with supporters claiming that Telangana Telugu's dialect, culture, and historical experiences were different from those of the coastal Andhra districts [32]. The desire for a separate state was further supported by claims of biased resource distribution, underrepresentation in government functions, and disregard for the region's infrastructure and educational requirements [33].

Movement: The linguistic variety of India has been a double-edged sword that has both benefited and hindered administrative coherence and unity. In response to these difficulties, the States Reorganization Act of 1956 was passed, with the intention of reorganizing the Indian states along linguistic lines. Nonetheless, the controversial decision to combine the Telugu-speaking areas of the former Hyderabad state with the Andhra state to establish Andhra Pradesh served as the impetus for the Telangana movement [34].

Reorganization Act: There was a great deal of activity leading up to Telangana's establishment, including large-scale demonstrations, hunger strikes, and political lobbying. Further complicating matters, the Srikrishna Committee, which was established by the Indian government in 2010 to investigate the demand for Telangana, presented a number of proposals but failed to offer a conclusive resolution. Nevertheless, the Telangana movement's tenacious efforts, spearheaded by the Telangana Rashtra Samithi (TRS) and other student and civil society organizations, ultimately forced the federal government to grant the demand for a separate state [35].

7. Role of language in demand for new states

In recent years, there have been increased demands for the creation of states on linguistic grounds, arguing that such reorganization could lead to good governance, better administration, and representation of various linguistic communities. For example, the division of Uttar Pradesh into four parts, the division of Gorkhaland from West Bengal, the division of Bodoland from Assam and the division of Mithilanchal from Bihar, and so on. These demands often arise from perceived neglect or underrepresentation of particular linguistic groups within bigger states, leading to calls for the creation of smaller, more manageable states where these languages and cultures can be better preserved and protected. One of the long-standing demands, for instance, is the creation of a new state called Vidarbha from Maharashtra. Supporters of this proposal claim that the development of the Marathi-speaking area has been overlooked in favour of the more prosperous and urbanized western regions of the state. Similar to this, there has been a push in southern India to create a Tulu Nadu by separating the Tulu-speaking region from Karnataka. The goal is to preserve the Tulu language and culture, which supporters believe are being overshadowed by the state's dominant Kannada language and culture [36].

Another example of linguistic movement that calls for the establishment of a distinct state for Nepali-speaking people in the hills of Darjeeling and Kalimpong is called Gorkhaland. The movement draws attention to the Gorkhas' unique cultural and linguistic identity, which sets them apart from West Bengal, a state where Bengali is the primary language. Even though the movement has not yet succeeded in creating a distinct state, it has created the Gorkhaland Territorial Administration, which has some autonomy [37].

In recent years, there has been a noticeable increase in the desire for Mithilanchal, a culturally and linguistically distinct area of Bihar, to be granted its own identity and the recognition of the Maithili language. This area, which is mostly in the states of Bihar and Jharkhand, has a rich cultural history and speaks Maithili as its primary language. The goal to protect and advance Mithilanchal's distinctive culture, language, and literature is the driving force behind the movement for linguistic recognition of the region.

Linguistic identity plays a significant role in the demand for these states, but other issues are often also important for division, like economic disparities, developmental neglect, and aspirations for greater political autonomy. Those who criticize linguistic reorganization argue that creating smaller states may not necessarily solve these root causes and could lead to increased administrative costs and potential interstate conflicts.

8. Challenges

Linguistic reorganization of states presents a number of challenges like ethnic, linguistic, cultural, and identity issues with political, economic, and administrative concerns, such as

- (i) **Ethnic Overlap:** It is challenging to establish precise administrative borders only on the basis of linguistic criteria since many regions contain overlapping ethnic groups and linguistic varieties. Language and identity are closely associated. When people are relocated to states where they might not feel represented or have a sense of belonging, boundary redrawing can cause problems with ethnic identification and assimilation [38].
- (ii) **Political and Social Tensions:** Inter-ethnic conflicts and aspirations for autonomy have occasionally been made worse by the language and ethnic boundaries that divide governments. Political parties may be against restructuring if they fear losing their support among voters or having their political influence reduced in reorganized areas.
- (iii) **Economic Inequities:** In any region, economic progress is frequently not uniform. Richer and poorer regions may be divided by linguistic rearrangement, creating economic inequality and causing conflict. The further division of resources, including minerals, water (ex Andhra – Telangana water dispute mainly from the Krishna and Godavari rivers, after the bifurcation of the erstwhile united Andhra Pradesh in 2014) and revenue sources, can become contentious, impacting economic stability and development prospects of new states.
- (iv) **Preservation of Minority Languages:** Smaller languages and dialects run the risk of becoming neglected, whilst bigger linguistic groupings may get full administrative and political recognition. So, a smaller group can be dissatisfied, leading to social unrest and demands for further subdivision.
- (v) **Inter-State Conflicts:** Linguistic restructuring has the potential to intensify or create new inter-state conflicts, particularly those involving strategically important or resource-

rich regions. Examples are the conflicts between Andhra Pradesh and Telangana over the city of Hyderabad and between Karnataka and Maharashtra over the Belgaum area.

9. Conclusion

Language politics is the way language and linguistic differences between peoples are dealt with in the political arena. Not much work has been done on the impact of linguistic diversity in the Indian political system and their negative impact on the developmental process. Though the Supreme Court reaffirmed the secular character of the Indian state, ruling that election candidates cannot seek votes on the grounds of their religion, caste, creed, community, or language of voters. According to Section 123(3) of the People's Representation Act of 1951, no candidate or his agent can appeal for votes on the grounds of religion, race, caste, community, or language. Any violation of this would be deemed a corrupt practice under the law, leading to the disqualification of the candidate [39].

Today, we consider the region of India, we see some changes in language used by common people per 2 km. It created a problem for policymakers to decide which language to use to make policy. It was discussed when our constitution framed Hindi (approximately 41% of speakers) as the official language and English as the associate official language (for 15 years later) with the majority of members. Politicization of language (with their own interests, politicians use language as a tool for polarizing their voters) emerges as a threat to our harmony. It is necessary to solve this problem immediately; otherwise, the demand of states on the basis of linguistic majority or linguistic minority created a hurdle in the overall development of India and also eroded our national feeling, which threatened our sovereignty. India's linguistic movements offer insight into the complicated relationship that exists between language, culture, and political identity. These initiatives have not only influenced India's linguistic landscape but also brought attention to the significance of cultural preservation and linguistic rights. The results of linguistic movements highlight the dynamic and ever-evolving character of linguistic politics in India, ranging from state reorganizations to modifications in official language laws. Various challenges like poverty, hunger, illiteracy, unemployment, etc. are faced today, and these are our priorities in facing such identity issues.

Acknowledgements: This work is based on the secondary data as a source from various books, research paper, articles, newspapers, and government reports.

Conflict of interests: This Paper has not any competing interests exist.

Author's contributions: The author Puja Kumari has designed and written the manuscript. The author Dr. Prerana Bhaduli has supervised the work.

Funding information: This Paper received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial or not-for-profit sectors.

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